

Is Carnival a National or Moral Festival?

Ms Fatimah Mohammed,
Chin Chin Road, Cunupia,
Trinidad and Tobago

fatimah.mohammed26@gmail.com

The Government of Trinidad and Tobago is distributing TT\$147 million this year for Carnival. It is no surprise that this celebration has been pushed into people's psyche as "the national festival." When the funds for all the other festivals and celebrations in the multi-ethnic country are added, they do not come close to the money being given away for Carnival.

It is Government-manufactured propaganda that Carnival is the "national festival" because many religious groups do not actively participate in Carnival festivities such as Adventists, Pentecostals, Muslims and Hindus. Moreover, only one group of people play steel pans, stick fighting, moko jumbies, blue devils and Canboulay. Mainly that group sings calypso, extempo and soca - another evidence that Carnival is not a national festival. Most people flock to beach houses and catch flights out of the country, which are totally booked months in advance for this season. Far more people seek to escape from Carnival than to participate in it.

It can be argued that Carnival is tearing apart the moral fabric of society to the detriment of our children (Kiddie Carnival and Carnival in schools). The masquerade of women in the streets can be summed up in four Bs: Bikini, Beads, Bottom and Breasts. Couples gyrating in public like dogs in heat have no respect for themselves, their parents, siblings, children and grandchildren. Carnival is destroying those who participate in it. Our women soca artistes dress and gyrate (wine) like pole dancers in a strip club.

The mood atmosphere and music are all about violence, destruction, alcoholism, nudity and sexuality expressed through the songs. e.g. Nailah Blackman X Stalk Ashley - Wine Low, Voice x Boyzie – SHAKEDOWN, Dj Private Ryan x Skinny Fabulous - Wine Pon Yuh Fren, BATTALION Music, Mical Teja - Runaway (D Ninja Roadmix), Problem Child - Mash Up (D Ninja X Muv Edit), Rome - Rum, Gyal & Money and Viking Ding Dong, Lyrikal & Travis World - Child Of Bacchanal. And remember \$147,000,000.00 is pushed to promote this orgy.